

THE ROLE OF MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF ENTERPRISES.

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Abstract - Management system is defined as a strategic process of an organization based on a comprehensive framework of instructions and well-designed set of guiding rules, for undergoing organizational operations for achieving organization targets. The set of directions included in the paper, refers to the key areas involved in effectively accomplishing organizational operational tasks.

Keywords - Management system, performance standard, performance measurement, quality process, resource planning, continuous improvement process, motivation, creativity.

All management decisions that relate to the relationship between a company and an employee affect the process of managing human resources, and accordingly this means that the practice of personnel management is noticeably closely related to business strategy.

Human resource management is a very multifaceted and complex phenomenon in its content and organizational and structural forms. But it acts not only as a complex structural and functional phenomenon, but also as a structurally dissected integrity, in which each element has a specific purpose and performs certain functions. This is a system of mechanisms and technologies for working with personnel to achieve certain results. In addition, this is the organization of the interaction of individual subsystems of staffing (training, professional development of personnel, legal, scientific, methodological, informational and financial support).

Thus, human resource management is an independently functioning system with its own principles, functions and powers, including labor resources planning, recruitment and selection of personnel, salary determination and development of a motivation system, professional orientation and adaptation of employees, staff training, workforce assessment, management training, and career management. Human resource management is not only a task for

personnel departments, it is up to managers of all levels to solve it. All of them face similar problems: they need to correctly understand and evaluate the behavior of subordinates and find ways to help the organization achieve its goals. A manager who understands how individual, group, and organizational characteristics affect people's attitudes to work and their behavior can experiment to see if changing one or more of these characteristics can improve the effectiveness of the organization as a whole, as well as individual employees and their groups of which it consists.

The study of the principles and rules of subordinate management helps managers to cope with the task of improving the effectiveness of the organization, providing them with a set of tools with which they can improve performance at the individual, group and organizational levels.

The manager performs four main functions: planning, organizing, leading, motivating, coordinating and controlling.

1.Functions of management.

Planning - defining organizational strategy; at the same time, managers decide what organizational goals should be achieved and how best to allocate and use resources for this. Planning is a complex and difficult task, since the decisions that managers must make are usually accompanied by many uncertainties. Because of these uncertainties, when deciding on specific actions, managers take risks. Knowledge of the basics of human resource management can help improve the quality of decisions made, increase the chances of success and reduce the risk inherent in planning and decision making, for at least three reasons. The study of people's behavior shows how decisions are made in an

organization and how the techniques used and the resulting conflicts affect the planning process. In addition, it becomes clear how the adoption of a group decision is manifested in planning, as well as how certain predilections can affect such a decision. And how the composition of the top management team of the organization can influence the planning process.

During the organization of work, managers set the structure of working relations that determine how members of the organization should cooperate with each other to achieve their goals. The organization process includes the distribution of employees into separate groups, teams or departments in accordance with the tasks performed.

In leadership, managers reward employees who do a good job and coordinate individuals and groups so that all members of the organization work towards common goals. Learning about the different methods of leadership and how leadership styles and the characteristics of an organization and all of its components fit together is an important aspect of human resource management.

Motivation is a process that begins with a physiological or psychological lack or need that activates behavior or creates an impulse (motive) aimed at achieving a specific goal or reward. Needs create incentives aimed at obtaining rewards, which is the basis of motivation. On fig. 2 shows a model of behavior motivation through needs and their satisfaction.

2. Model of behavior motivation through needs.

Coordination, as a separate function of management, has been advocated by many authorities including Henri Fayol. However, coordination, being all pervasive and encompassing every function of management, is considered to be

more an important managerial essence than a separate management function. Poor coordination is attributed to failure in performance of all the above-listed management functions.

Coordination deals with harmonizing work relations and efforts at all levels for achieving some common purpose. It may be described as unifying and achieving harmony among individual efforts for the purpose of accomplishing group goals. The whole idea of coordination is to adjust, reconcile, and synchronize individual efforts so that group efforts become more effective and help to achieve some common objectives.

By exercising control, managers monitor and evaluate individual, group and organizational performance to determine the extent to which goals are achieved. If this happens, managers can focus on maintaining and improving performance; if not, they need to take corrective action. The monitoring function also allows managers to assess how well they are performing in other functions: planning, organizing, and directing.

Conclusion and suggestions

To ensure sound control mechanism in a big enterprise, certain requirements have to be fulfilled. Appropriate control devices with the arrangement of prompt way of rectification are essential. A control system is of forward looking nature because many eventualities cannot be instantaneous. It is very much needed for a good control mechanism to focus attention on critical variances. Not only to find out the deviation but also to indicate the strategic points where control is necessary is the characteristic of a sound control system. This is control by exception. It is necessary that controlling should be simple, economic and suggestive. Flexibility and objectivity with proper organizational pattern constitute the prerequisite for a good control system. It will be no exaggeration to comment that control is vital for an organisation. The bigger the size of the organisation, more the need for sound control. It is a process to be kept always on alert, so everything pre-planned is accomplished in the way it has been visualized; any indication of deviation has to be rectified in advance. Prevention is better than cure — this should be the maxim for a sound control system. The complexities of modern business with its giant size call for better controlling and as the days are passing the significance of control as a function of management is increasing.

